

Impact of Training on ASHAs in Selected Districts of Madhya Pradesh

V P Goswami, Shailesh Rai, Sanjay Dixit, Satish Sarose, Ruchita Banseria
Department of Community Medicine, MGM Medical College, Indore

(Received: April, 2016)

(Accepted: June, 2016)

ABSTRACT

A cross sectional study amongst ASHAs (Accredited Social Health Activists) working under National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) was conducted in randomly selected two districts each from Indore and Ujjain divisions of the state of Madhya Pradesh. Data was collected with the help of Pre & Post-test evaluation of trainees, feedback from trainees, passive observation of training centers, and interview of trainees by using semi structured questionnaire. Work experience of ASHAs in Ujjain Division was less than 5 years amongst almost 76% as compare to Indore division where it was 53% only. In Ujjain division 150 (31.91 %) ASHAs were not trained in first four modules of ASHA training as compared to 12.15 % (62) ASHA from Indore division. The satisfaction level between Indore and Ujjain divisions were different with a higher satisfaction level in Indore division as compared to Ujjain division ASHAs. p value < 0.05 . Complete training and infrastructure had significant impact on knowledge of ASHAs about the new born health care e.g. Breast feeding, fever, hypothermia, malnutrition and danger signs as well as other indicators amongst sick children.

KEY WORDS: accredited social health activists (ASHA), impact, training

INTRODUCTION:

Developing countries especially India has seen so many ups and down particularly in health sectors before and after Independence. Many health programs in health sectors have failed in the past or could not achieve desired objectives. Therefore recognizing the importance of Health in the process of economic and social development and improving the quality of life of our citizens, a paradigm shift took place in India and the Government of India decided to launch a National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) to address the health needs of rural population, especially the vulnerable sections of society. Hence to overcome this situation a new band of community based functionaries, named as Accredited Social Health Activist (ASHA), is functional to fill this void.

The National Rural Health Mission (NRHM)

launched in April, 2005 has completed seven years of implementation and is now commencing its second phase. The ASHA programme was introduced as a key component of the community processes intervention. Over the seven year period, the ASHA programme has emerged as the largest community health worker programme in the world, and is considered a critical contributor to enabling people's participation in health^[1,2,3]

ASHA (Accredited Social Health Activist) is a health activist in the community who creates awareness on health and its social determinants and mobilize the community towards local health planning and increased utilization and accountability of the existing health services^[4]. They act as a 'bridge' between the rural people and health service outlets and would play a central role, in achieving national health and population policy goals^[5,6]. The effectiveness of ASHA worker largely depends on the training and support from both the health system and the community^[7].

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

It was a cross sectional study. The study sites

Corresponding Author: Dr. V.P. Goswami
Block B-2, Flat 301, Scheme 98, Samvad
Nagar Near Navlakha Square, Indore -
452001
Phone No.: +91 8989733463
E-mail: drvpgoswami@gmail.com

included: randomly selected two districts each from Indore and Ujjain divisions of the state of Madhya Pradesh namely Indore, Jhabua and Dewas Neemuch; and the ASHA training centers run by NGOs in each district namely, Training center Jeevan Jyoti Prashikshan Kendra, labor colony Rau, main AB road run by NGO Bhartiya Gramin Mahila Sangh (BGMS) Indore; Training center ASRA, 26, Badridham Nagar Dewas (M.P.) run by NGO Asra Samajik Lok Kalian Samiti Dewas; Training center Kaku Residency Ranapur Road in front of PG College, Jhabua run by NGO Ambika Shiksha Sansthan Kalyan Samiti, Bhopa and Training center Maheshwari Bhavan, Neemuch by NGO kailash Boriwal Sahaj Samaj Utthan Samiti, 7 Parda complex, Near Central bank, kamal Chowk, Neemuch. The Study Population was: 980 ASHAs after their skill based training (6th & 7th modules) at their District training Centre. The study was conducted for a period of 24 Months (i.e. from January 2013 to December 2014). The study subjects were: ASHAs (Accredited Social Health Activists). The study tools included: Pre & Post-test questionnaire for trainees, Feedback form for trainees, Observation checklist for assessment of infrastructure, staff, teaching aids and other facility at training centers. No violation of ethic was visible as the study was enquiry driven and non-interventional in nature. The questionnaires were redesigned & validated (pretested) in study areas with an appropriate small sample size of ASHAs. The data collected were analyzed through percentages and frequencies in which the data were presented in table formats, pie charts and histograms which were obtained using Excel and using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science).

RESULTS:

Training plan and process at all four training centers was almost similar. Since ASHA training had to go a long way (several months) as each ASHA of the respective district had to be trained, the plan for training was made well in advance for all ASHAs divided in several batches, each batch with 22 to 30 ASHAs.

There were lack of facilities at Dewas district training center of Ujjain division. It did not have connectivity & accessibility, separate dormitories and mess for residing trainees instead the lecture halls itself were utilized as hostels in the non-training hours and in the night. The toilets/ bathroom were attached to lecture halls itself and no other separate toilet facility was available. A small dining hall was available which

was reserved only for trainers.

There was no facility of library, health clinic and outdoor space for recreation and facility of crèche at most of the training center.

Participants come by their own convenience to the training center. Training was conducted as per the schedule issued by state govt. The training schedule was of five continuous days, the 4th day of which was fixed for field training and 5th day for evaluation/ theory and practical exams. Accommodation and food facility was provided free of cost (govt. fund) to the trainees and trainers. After the training hours, the trainees were left for recreational activities and group discussions. Two trainers stay at the training center in night to keep vigil over the trainees and help them whenever required. The Cheques of TA/DA were distributed to each participant on the last day of training before the trainees leave from training center.

Out of 980 ASHAs included in the study almost 93% were married and remaining 7% were unmarried/ widowed. The mean age of ASHAs was 26.5 years with a range of 17 to 58 years in both the divisions. About 3/4th (72%) of ASHAs had eligible qualification of class 8th and above while the rest (28%) were not eligible, and selected due to unavailability of qualified candidates. Out of total 510 ASHAs in Indore division 160(16.32%) and in Ujjain division it was 114 out of 470 (11.63%) of ASHAs who did not have the minimum qualification (class 8th pass) required to be selected as ASHA. Almost more than 40% of the ASHAs had working experience of less than 5 year. Average Monthly Household Income (in Rs.) was also very less and it was more in districts Ujjain division (4896/-Rs) as compare to Indore division (2960/-Rs).

In Ujjain division 150 ASHA (31. 91 %) ASHAs were not trained in first four modules of ASHA training as compare to 12.15 % (62) ASHA from Indore division.

The satisfaction regarding completion of training objectives were compared for Indore and Ujjain Divisions. The satisfaction level between Indore and Ujjain divisions were different with a higher satisfaction level in Indore division as compared to Ujjain division ASHAs. p value < 0.05.

DISCUSSION:

Government through NRHM is making lots of effort to strengthen the ASHA programme by selection and training process. This study has been conducted to know the effect of training (presently skill based

Table 1: Facilities available at different District training centers.

S. No.	Facilities	Indore		Ujjain Division	
		Indore	Jhabua	Dewas	Neemuch
1	Building	Pucca	Pucca	Pucca	Pucca
2	Connectivity & accessibility	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
3	Lectures halls (adequate capacity)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	Light & ventilation of halls	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal
5	AV aids, black/white board , LCD	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	Separate hostel facility	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
7	Dining hall and mess	Yes	No	No	Yes
8	Sufficient indoor & outdoor space	Yes	No	No	No
9	Separate toilet facility	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
10	Safe Drinking water	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
11	Health care facility / clinic	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
12	Library	Yes	No	No	Yes
13	Crèche facility/children park	No	No	No	No
14	Notice board	No	No	No	Yes

Table 2: Observation of the trainings:

S. No.	Key findings	Indore Division		Ujjain Division	
		Indore	Jhabua	Dewas	Neemuch
1	Inauguration session as per schedule	No	No	No	No
2	All the participants come before the start of training session	No	No	No	No
3	Registration of the participants	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
4	Distribution of training kit and stationary to the ASHAs	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	Batch size limited to 30 participants	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	Formal introduction and recap of the previous training session	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
7	Trainers stick to the topics as per schedule	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	Cross questioning from participants and explanation by trainers	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
9	Orientation of all the participants throughout the lecture	No	No	No	No
10	Availability charts, models, dummies etc	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
11	Daily Assignments to the trainees	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
12	All participants go to field visits	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
13	All participants go through theory and practical exams	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
14	Got the remunerations/TA /DA for training	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Table 3: Study Sample demographic Profile of ASHAs in the selected districts:

S. No.	Characters	Indore Division		Total	Ujjain Division		Total
		Indore	Jhabua		Dewas	Neemuch	
1	No. of ASHAs Surveyed	270 (27.55%)	240 (24.4%)	510 (52.04%)	310 (31.63%)	160 (16.32%)	470 (47.95%)
2	Average Age of ASHAS (in years)	27	26	26.5 Average	28	25	26.5 Average
3	Average no. of Married ASHAs	252 (93.33%)	239 (99.5%)	491 (96.30%)	284 (92%)	133 (83.2%)	417 (87.5.5%)
4	% Educated below 8th Grade	28% (76)	35% (84)	16.32% (160)	24% (74)	25% (40)	11.63% (114)
5	Average Monthly Household Income (in Rs.)	3665	2255	2960/-	4192	5600	4896/-
6	Average No. of Years of Service	05.60	3.5	04.55	04.03	05.00	4.51

Table 4: Training status (prior training of first four modules).

S. No	Status	Indore	Jhabua	Total (%)	Dewas	Neemuch	Total (%)
1.	Trained in 1-4 modules	241	207	448 (87.84%)	189	131	320 (68.08%)
2.	Not trained in 1-4 modules	29	33	62 (12.15%)	121	29	150 (31.91)
	Total	270	240	510	310	160	470 (100%)

Table 5: Comparison of Indore and Ujjain Division for satisfaction regarding completion of training objectives:

Two sample proportion	Indore Division (Total -510)		Ujjain Division (Total -470)	
	Satisfied	Satisfied	z score	p value
Objectives:				
To take care of the new-born, support and help the mother to breastfeed, and to keep the baby warm.	450	305	8.90	0.0001
Counsel mother for breastfeeding and Emphasize importance of early and exclusive breastfeeding	425	290	7.77	0.0001
Identify the new-born with fever and hypothermia and Teach mothers how to keep the new-born warm	415	296	6.53	0.0001
Communicate essential messages for prevention of malnutrition, advice on feeding and on prevention of illness, and on access to health and nutrition services	475	345	8.49	0.0001
Identify general danger signs among sick children, recognize symptoms of common illnesses and Enable prompt referral.	468	365	6.20	0.0001

training, 6th & 7th module) on ASHAs knowledge, skills and their work behavior.

Currently second round of skill based training (6th and 7th module) is in process in most of the districts of Madhya Pradesh including Indore Jhabua, Dewas and Neemuch. This is a five days residential training being organized only at district headquarters of each district by selected non-governmental organization for each district.

Training centers at all the four districts had micro plan issued by government and a written schedule for training. All the centers followed the training plan and schedule but there was delay in the start-up of session on the first day of training. It was found that most of ASHAs came late at the training center on first day instead of a day before in the evening as per guidelines.

After training center evaluation, different components eg. reaction, learning /knowledge were evaluated on 980 ASHAs, 270 from Indore, 310 from Dewas, 240 from Jhabua and 160 from Neemuch. The average age of ASHAs was around 26.5 years in both the divisions which is lower compared to study done by Bajpayi N. et al (2010)^[8] in Bihar (31 years), Uttar Pradesh (31 years), Rajasthan (33 years) and Chhattisgarh (32). However it was similar to the study by Srivastav DK et al (2009)^[9] in which more than half of the ASHAs were in age group 20-29 years. It is also lower compared to study done by Abel M et al, 29.8^[2] years. 26.5% of ASHAs were below the minimum age criteria i.e. less 25 years of age, recruited due to unavailability of other candidate.

More than one third, 160 (31.50%) ASHAs had less than essential qualification (class 8th) i.e. was below class 8th pass. The proportion is similar to the study done by Bajpayi N. et al^[8] in 2010 where 28% of the ASHAs from Chhattisgarh were below class 8th standard. A study by Bhatt H, et al^[10] in Uttarakhand in 2012 also revealed that most of the ASHAs were qualified 8th and above and only few were qualified below 8th.

The reaction or feedback indicated that satisfaction level between Indore and Ujjain divisions were different with a higher satisfaction level in Indore division (85%), as compared to ASHAs of Ujjain division (68%), with objectives i.e. know how to perform different activities for new born care, care of sick child, counsel mothers for baby feeding, prevent new born from hypothermia and educate mothers for prevention of child malnutrition.

The reaction was similar as in study by Bhatt H, et al^[10] in Uttarakhand in year 2012, where most of

the ASHAs admit that the training is beneficial, but nearly half of them don't consider the training to be adequate. Also in study by Bajpayi N. et al^[8] in 2010 most of the trainees were satisfied with training activity and those who were not satisfied wanted a repeat training. 49% of the ASHAs from Dewas and Jhabua complained of inadequate facility for residential training, space and bathroom /toilet facility. There was no facility of library, health clinic and outdoor space for recreation and facility of crèche at all the training center.

Most of the participants have adequate knowledge about the new born care and danger signs etc. The result was similar to study by Mahyavanshi DK, et al, 2011^[11] in which around 90% of ASHAs had poor knowledge regarding hypothermia and kangaroo mother care, 80% had poor knowledge regarding neonatal infection and 86.16% of ASHA workers had poor knowledge regarding referral condition and when and where to refer the baby. Also around 70% had poor knowledge regarding correct breast feeding practices, and nearly 86% and 71% had poor knowledge of problems regarding breast feeding and complimentary feeding respectively. In another study by Srivastav SR, et al, 2012^[12] evaluated the knowledge of trained ASHAs about child Health care in which 15-20% of ASHAs were not aware of the danger signals of dehydration, 20-30% were unaware of danger symptoms/ signs of pneumonia in spite of undergoing training. Around 30-40% of ASHAs were not aware of the dangerous AEFI (after effects following immunization).

CONCLUSION:

Training had significant impact on knowledge of ASHAs about the new born health care eg. Breastfeeding, fever and hypothermia, malnutrition and danger signs among sick children. Those who are trained gave satisfactory response regarding completion of training objectives. So complete training of all the modules is most important and required process of knowledge improvement of ASHAs which is evident from low level of satisfaction in Ujjain division where more than 1/3rd were not trained in module 1-4 and had significant lack of training facilities.

REFERENCES:

1. Guidelines for Community Processes 2013, NRHM, Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. Assessed through <http://nhsrcindia.org/index>.

- php.
2. AbelM, Almas S, Brown W, Sahni HV, Serotta R. "Effect of Supportive Supervision on ASHAs' Performance under IMNCI in Rajasthan" In collaboration with Indian Institute of Health Management Research (IIHMR) Jaipur.KCCI / 2009-08 available from <http://www.kcci.org.in>.
 3. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. National Health Policy (1983). Available from <http://www.planningcommission.nin.in>.
 4. Ministry of Health and Family Welfare. National Health Policy (MoHFW) (2005c). ASHA. Government of India. <http://en.wikipedia.org>.
 5. Government of India. National Rural Health Mission (2005-2012) Mission Document. New Delhi: Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, 2005. Available at [http://www.Mohfw.nic.in/NRHM/mission document .pdf](http://www.Mohfw.nic.in/NRHM/mission_document.pdf)
 6. National Institute of Health & Family Welfare report "A study to Assess Factors at Peripheral Level for Effective Implementation of ASHA Scheme" in Utter Pradesh.
 7. Shashank KJ,. Angadi MM, Masali KA, Wajantri P, Bhat S, Jose AP. "a study to evaluate working Profile of accredited social Health activist (ASHA) and to Assess their knowledge about Infant health care". IJCRR. 2013; 5(12): 97-103.
 8. NirupamBajpai and Ravindra H. Dholakia Working Paper No. 1 May 2011 "Improving the performance of accredited social health activists in India" WORKING PAPERS SERIES Columbia Global Centers | South Asia, Columbia University available at http://globalcenters.columbia.edu/files/cgc/pictures/Improving_the_Performance_of_ASHAs_in_India_CGCSA_Working_Paper_1.pdf
 9. Srivastava DK, Prakash S, Adish V, Nair KS, Gupta S, Nandan D. A Study of interference of ASHA with the community and the services providers in Eastern Uttar Pradesh. Indian Journal of Public Health. 2009; 53(3):133-6.
 10. Hema B. A rapid appraisal of functioning of ASHA under NRHM in Uttarakhand, India, 2012. Accessed through : <http://cooperation.epfl.ch/page-91580-fr.html>
 11. Mahyavanshi DK, Patel MG, Kartha G, Purani SK, Nagar SS. "A cross sectional study of the knowledge, attitude and practice of ASHA workers regarding child health (under five years of age) in Surendranagar district". Healthline 2011; 2(2): 50.
 12. Shrivastava SR, Shrivastava PS. Evaluation of trained accredited social health activist (ASHA) workers regarding their knowledge and attitude and practice about child health. Rural and Remote Health, 2012;12(4):2099 (online) available: <http://www.rrh.org.au>

Cite this article as: Goswami VP, Rai S, Dixit S, Sarose S, Banseria R: Impact of Training on ASHAs in Selected Districts of M.P. PJSR ;2016;9(2):50-55.

Source of Support : Nil, **Conflict of Interest:** None declared.